

IMPACT OF BLOCK CHAIN SECURITY SYSTEM IN CURRENT SCENARIO

¹ Shilpa S Jadimath,

¹ Research Scholar,

¹Department of Computer Application,

¹ Chetan College of Commerce and BCA, Hubballi, Karnataka

Abstract: One of the newer technologies in the area of information technology is the block chain. Block chain is a distributed database system that is run by numerous nodes and is decentralized, traceable, temper proof, and trustworthy. With the promise of more skills and more resilience, block chain is employed in a variety of applications beyond bit coin or electronic money, including financial transactions, healthcare, insurance, IoT, manufacturing, and education. Numerous news stories and public statements concerning its objectives, alliances, creation, and application have been made over the previous few years. However, discussions on the most crucial elements of block chain security, difficulties, and regulations have been raised globally. This review study examined 80 research papers with a focus on block chain security challenges. The notion of block chain ecosystems, the division of block chains, the implementation of block chains, and finally security concerns and block chain difficulties are noteworthy works in this review article. This review article will be beneficial for new research projects and block chain safety-related concerns.

Index Terms – Block Chain, Impact, Benefits, Current Scenario, Comparison.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Block chain security is a complete risk management system for a block chain network that employs assurance services, best practices, and cyber security frameworks to lower risks against fraud and assaults. Block chain technology has the potential to revolutionize how companies conduct business and interact with their clients, competitors, and authorities. Using the alias Satoshi Nakamoto, a person or group of persons in 2019 published a paper, presented a new crypto currency called "bit coin," and proposed a peer-to-peer networking (P-to-P) solution for online fund transfers from one party to another without the use of a third party or trusted party. It is an ecosystem that is expanding more quickly to alter technology concepts everywhere. Block chain is a sort of distributed ledger technology that acts as a distributed and immutable ledger for many types of transactions, transferring ownership, maintaining transaction records, tracing assets, and ensuring transparency, trust, and security. Although the majority of people think that one of its advantages is the built-in resilience of cyber security, the technical platform is still not completely secure and free from cyber attacks.

Due of its potential uses in the future for other customers, other firms, and regulators, entrepreneurs, investors, and legislators are now focusing more on this newest cutting-edge technology. Therefore, it will involve security risks that include serious consequences as a result of members in the block chain network engaging in malicious or negligent behavior, where social engineering techniques are employed to get sensitive credentials. Just a security compromise might have a significant impact on all valued assets on the block chain, exposing national legal and regulatory violations.

One of the biggest inventions of the twenty-first century has been block chain technology, which has influenced everything from manufacturing to education and the financial sector. Block chain has the potential to significantly improve the financial, IoT, supply chain, voting, healthcare, insurance, education, and other sectors. It has several unique characteristics to reduce cyber-security concerns, and the security features include

1. Block chains strengthen the network's resilience by preventing single-point failures.
2. The consensus method used by block chain ensures the integrity and transparency of the ledger.
3. It is extremely difficult for hackers or other attackers to implant or deploy malware.

On the other hand, some of the most significant issues with block chain security, such as endpoint, scalability, regulatory, third party vendor, and inadequate testing, cannot be disregarded. Another way that attackers or groups of attackers can seize control of the block chain network is through a 51% attack. We will focus on the security concerns and difficulties associated with block chain technology in this post. The number of active block chains is increasing daily and at an exponential rate. With several hundred additional non-crypto currencies block chains, there are more than 10,000 active crypto currencies as of 2022.

(Fig. 1.1 BLOCK CHAIN SECURITY SYSTEM)

II. USES OF BLOCK CHAINS:

Blocks in the Bit currency block chain, as we already know, store information about financial transactions. More than 10,000 other crypto currency systems are currently active on the block chain. But it turns out that the block chain is also a trustworthy method for preserving information about other kinds of transactions.

Numerous businesses, including Walmart, Pfizer, AIG, Siemens, Unilever, and a host of others, have already used block chain technology. To track the route that food products take to reach their destinations, for instance, IBM developed the Food Trust block chain.

1. **Finance and banking: Banking** is one sector that might stand to gain the most from incorporating block chain into its operations. Financial institutions are only open during regular business hours, which are typically five days per week. As a result, if you attempt to deposit a check on Friday at 6 p.m., you probably won't see the funds in your account until Monday morning. Due to the enormous volume of transactions that banks must settle, even if you do make your deposit within business hours, it may still take one to three days for the transaction to be verified. The block chain, on the other hand, is always active.
2. **Currency:** For digital currencies like Bit coin, block chain serves as the foundation. The Federal Reserve is in charge of the US dollar. A user's data and money are technically subject to the whims of their bank or government under this

system of central power. The private information of a client is in danger if their bank is hacked. The value of the client's money may be in jeopardy if their bank fails or if they reside in a nation with a volatile government. A number of failing banks were partially bailed out in 2008 with taxpayer funds. These are the concerns that led to the original conception and development of Bit coin.

3. **Healthcare:** Medical records for patients can be safely stored by healthcare professionals using block chain technology. The ability to write a medical record into the block chain after it has been created and signed gives patients the assurance that the record cannot be altered. These private health records might be encoded and kept on the block chain with a secret key so that only specific people can access them, maintaining their privacy.
4. **Record of Property:** If you've ever spent time in your local recorder's office, you are aware of how time-consuming and ineffective the process of documenting property rights is. A tangible deed must now be handed to a government worker at the county recording office, where it will be manually put into the public index and central database. Claims to the property that are in dispute must be compared to the public index.
5. **Smart Contracts:** A contract agreement can be facilitated, verified, or negotiated using a smart contract, which is computer code that can be incorporated into the block chain. Users accept a set of terms under which smart contracts operate. The terms of the Agreement shall automatically be carried out upon the satisfaction of such requirements.
6. **Supplies Chains:** Suppliers can utilize block chain to record the origins of the materials they have purchased, similar to the IBM Food Trust example. This would enable businesses to confirm the legitimacy of both their own products and well-known labels like "Organic," "Local," and "Fair Trade."
7. **Voting:** As was already noted, a contemporary voting system could be facilitated by block chain. Block chain voting has the ability to end election fraud and increase voter turnout, as demonstrated during the West Virginia midterm elections in November 2018. This use of block chain would make it nearly difficult to meddle with votes. The block chain protocol would also uphold electoral openness while lowering the number of people required conducting an election and giving officials access to results almost immediately. As a result, there would be no need for recounts and no legitimate reason to be concerned that election fraud would occur.

III. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN A PRIVATE BLOCK CHAIN AND A PUBLIC BLOCK CHAIN:

A public block chain, sometimes referred to as an open or permission less block chain, allows anyone to join the network and set up a node without restriction. These block chains need to be safeguarded using encryption and a consensus mechanism like proof of work because of how open they are (PoW).

On the other hand, a private or permissioned block chain needs each node to be vetted before joining. The layers of security do not need to be as thick because nodes are presumed to be trustworthy.

IV. BENEFITS OF BLOCK CHAINS:

1. **Reliability of the Chain:** A network of thousands of computers approves transactions on the block chain network. As a result, practically all human involvement in the verification process is eliminated, which reduces human error and ensures that the information is recorded accurately.
2. **Cost Savings:** Consumers typically pay a bank to confirm a transaction, a notary to sign a document, or a preacher to officiate a wedding. Third-party verification is no longer necessary, and with it, it's accompanying costs.

3. **Decentralization:** *Block chain doesn't save any of its data in a single place. Instead, a network of computers copies and disseminates the block chain. Each time a fresh block is inserted into the block chain, Each machine on the network changes its copy of the block chain to reflect the modification.*
4. **Speedy Transactions:** *The settlement of transactions made through a centralised authority may take many days. For instance, if you try to deposit a check on Friday night, you could not actually see any money in your account until Monday morning.*
5. **Private Transactions:** *A lot of block chain networks function as public databases, making the network's transaction history available to anybody with an Internet connection. Users can see transaction data, but they cannot access information that would identify the users who made the transactions.*
6. **Secure Transactions:** *After a transaction is recorded, the block chain network must confirm the legitimacy of the transaction. On the block chain, thousands of computers scramble to verify if the purchase's specifics are accurate.*
7. **Transparency:** *The majority of block chains use only open-source code. Its code can therefore be viewed by anybody and everyone. This enables auditors to assess the security of digital currencies like Bit coin.*
8. **Banking for Unbanked People:** *The fact that everyone may utilize block chain and bit coin, regardless of racial origin, gender, or cultural background, is perhaps its most profound feature. The World Bank estimates that 1.7 billion adults do not have bank accounts or any other way to keep their money or assets safe.*
9. **Cost of technology:** *Block chain technology is not free, despite the fact that it can save customers money on transaction costs. For instance, the PoW mechanism used by the bit coin network to validate transactions demands a tremendous amount of processing power. The power used by the millions of computers connected to the bit coin network is comparable to what Norway and Ukraine use each year in the real world.*
10. **Data inefficiency and speed:** *Bit coin serves as the ideal case study for the potential shortcomings of block chains. A new block can be added to the block chain in around 10 minutes using Bit coin's PoW method.*
11. **Unlawful Activity:** *While the block chain network's confidentiality shields users from attacks and protects their privacy, it also permits illicit trade and activities. While the block chain network's confidentiality safeguards users' privacy and prevents hacks, it also enables criminal activities and trading.*
12. **Regulation:** *Concerns regarding governmental control of digital currencies have been voiced by many in the crypto community. Governments might theoretically make it illegal to own crypto currencies or participate in their networks, even though it is becoming more and more difficult to stop something like Bit coin as its decentralized network grows.*

V. CONCLUSION:

Due to its decentralized platform and peer-to-peer network, the block chain is without a doubt a rising technology in recent years, particularly in the field of information technology. There is a significant and extraordinary potential for block chain for many businesses, which will support the creation of such a dependable, secure, and immutable system in the future. While there are still concerns that need to be resolved, some of them have already been handled as the new technology paradigm for block chain applications has become more robust. Despite having a large number of benefits, it has various security weaknesses that have been emphasized in this article. The regulator must handle the appropriate regulatory concerns for this cutting-edge technology, and businesses must be prepared for the use of block chain technology, which could lessen the system's impact.

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